

Reward Management Culture: A Predictor of Business Educator's Job Retention in Nigerian Colleges of Education

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Abstract

The study investigates reward management culture as a predictor of job retention of Business educators in Colleges of Education in Edo/ Delta States in Nigeria. The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the extent to which reward management culture correlate job retention of Business educators in Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta States. Two research questions guided the study while a hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. A correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. The study population comprised 133 Business educators in the public Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta States. There was no sampling because the population was manageable; hence, a census. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts of measurement and evaluation all from the University of Benin, Edo State. The reliability of instrument was established using Cronbach alpha statistics that yielded total alpha value of 0.80. Pearson product moment correlation was used to analyzed both the research questions while Multiple Regression Analysis was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. the overall correlation between reward management culture and job retention of business educators found some of the reward management culture such as remuneration positive while, career development showed a negative and moderate correlation with job retention of Business educators. Based on the findings, it was concluded that reward management culture variables are determinants of business educator's job retention in Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta States. Sequel to the conclusion it was recommended among others that Colleges of Education should strive to invest in the training/development of business educators which will not only help maintain their core competencies but will also enhance their job satisfaction and retention.

Keywords: Reward Management, Culture, Attraction, Business Educators, College of Education

Introduction

The policy that guides the establishment of Colleges of Education as revered in the National Policy on Education with regards to the professional preparation of teachers for basic education in Nigeria

has a number of objectives. Among which are: to produce highly motivated, conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of our educational system; to encourage further the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers; to help teachers to fit into social life of the community and the society at large and enhance their commitment to national goals; to provide teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and make them adaptable to changing situations and to enhance teachers' commitment to the teaching profession (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013).

One of the programmes run in Colleges of Education is business education, where business educators are the major operators of the programme. They transform the business education curricula into reality at this level of education. The main objective of the business education programme is to empower individuals with desirable skills, abilities, knowledge, and competencies to perform specific functions such as to teach and/or become self-sufficient and self-reliant in the competitive business world. To achieve these objectives, there is need for adequate human capital base in terms of academic of the right quality and quantity since no education system may rise above the quality of its teachers. The college's human resource policy ought to guarantee the attraction of business educators for sustainability of the right academic standard of business education programme.

The overall process of job retention of the highly skilled business educators that will help to realize this noble objective could be contingent on the reward management culture prevailing in the colleges. This is because business educators are the type of manpower needed in different aspects of the economy as they can function as administrators, ICT experts, financial analyst, production, and material management experts. They have a wide range of choice of employment opportunities if they are qualified and competent and if the reward is right in accordance with service delivery. Reward can be thought as the total package given by an employer to an employee for services rendered towards the realization of organizational objectives. Reward could be used as a way of strengthening good behaviours among employees as well as productivity. Reward management is concerned with the formulation and implementation of strategies and policies that aim at rewarding people fairly, equitably and consistently in accordance with their value to the organization (Armstrong, 2010). It consists of analysing and controlling employee remuneration, compensations and all the other benefits such as retirement plan, hospitalization program for the employees. It is aimed at creating and efficiently operating a reward structure for an organization To meet their obligations, business educators and management of the colleges must develop a relationship that will fulfil the continually changing needs of both parties. At the minimum the college expects business educators to perform reliably the tasks assigned to them at the standards set for them, and to follow the rules that have been established to govern the workplace. Management often expects more than that. They expect business educators to take initiative, supervise themselves, continue to learn new skills, and be responsive to the college needs. On the other hand, business educators expect their colleges to provide fair pay, safe working condition, offer clear career path and fair treatment. In other words, business educators also often expect

more, depending on the strength of their needs for security, status, involvement, power and responsibility. The expectations of both parties vary from organization to organization depending on their culture. The management of the college however can attract and retain top and experienced business educators depending on the dynamics of their internal and external equity regarding their reward policies and practices.

The management of reward system in the college therefore ought to be developed to attract, motivate and retain the business educators. It is an important aspect of human resources management because a well-designed reward system will lead towards organizational productivity and employee's satisfaction. The management of reward system in an organization over time could be referred to as reward management culture. Silbert (2005) concludes that it is important that rewards have a lasting impression on the employee and continue to sustain the employees' perception that they are valued in the organization. This assertion is amplified by the views of Olakunle and Ehi (2008), that if reward plan is perceived to be unfair and unrealistic, it may pose a negative effect as a motivator. Hence, the essence of reward management culture in College of Education is to ensure sound policies and practices as regards reward implementation that could attract, retain and motivate the highly skilled business educators in the Colleges of Education.

Employee retention is a process in which the employees are encouraged to remain with the organization for the maximum period of time or until the completion of the project. Mark, Nicholas and Douglas (2016) viewed retention as an obligation to continue to do business or exchange with a particular company on an ongoing basis. According to Stauss, Chojnacki, Decker and Hoffman (2001) employee retention refer to customer liking, identification, commitment, trust, readiness to recommend, and repurchase intentions, with the first four being emotional-cognitive retention constructs, and the last two being behavioural intentions. Managing and retaining promising employees is an important fundamental mean of achieving competitive advantage among organizations (Walker 2001). Parkinson (1990) in Mark, et al., (2016) defines employee retention as the efforts by which employers attempt to retain employees in their workforce. In this sense employee retention becomes a strategy rather than an outcome. Organization's strategists develop employee retention as a strategy with focus of gaining competitive advantage that is aligned to the overall organization's strategy. There are various high-performance environments that share a serious devotion to results after employees are retained. This calls for examining approaches that can be used to retain critical employees. Nurturing from entry level, a new hire and then to high performing and committed employees requires organization to understand requirements of positive work environment. According to Holland, Sheehan and De Cierr (2007), Human Capital, gives competitive edge due to its uniqueness. As such, it is one of the resources that work as a pillar for an organization. Focus has therefore shifted to the employees of the organizations. Employees play an important role in organizations; they are the greatest resource an organization can have, and it is through their involvement that the organization can become competitive. (Sempene, Rieger & Roodt,2002).

Therefore, the rewards practices in the college ought to be designed to match the services rendered by the highly skilled business educators to avoid job dissatisfaction that often leads to their mobility. According to Norah (2017), the various rewards management practices in human resource management that may constitute the culture that can attract and retain business educators may include: Career development, employee remuneration, employee recognition, promotion, safety and security of employees, job specification and job enrichment. These abound in typical business organizations and are also expected to abound in colleges of education and applicable to business educators; they are attracted and retained by the reward management culture operating in these colleges. Some specific reward management practices that are embedded in the culture include: Career development initiatives and employee`s remuneration.

Career development can be perceived of as a lifelong process of managing learning, work, leisure, and transitions to move toward a personally determined and evolving preferred future. It is believed that most organization adopt career development in response to pragmatic human resource concerns because they believe it will help in ensuring continued supply and retention of qualified and talented employee. Therefore, active career development in Colleges of Education may serve as an attraction and retention tool to keep the best talent/ highly skilled business educators within its fold. This may be possible by investing in their future growth and showing business educator the path to fulfil their career. Career development programs will involve, periodic assessment be carried out by the human resource departments of Colleges of Education to ascertain the skills, abilities, competencies and the improvement made by business educators.

Career development is a motivational incentive that promotes employee`s retention and productivity (Musa, Ahmed, & Bala, 2014). Career development comprises of resolute efforts bound for evaluating an employee`s competences identifying possible career advancement for that worker and developing and implementing different types of training programmes and experience to organize that individual for job enlargement and enrichment. In most businesses, its gradually obvious that career development programs are cost justified in the same conditions as initial programs; meaning each endorsement contributes to enhanced deployment of workers overall organizational operation and development (Mapelu & Jumah, 2013). The significance of career development is as a result to match an employee's career path with opportunities and challenges experienced within the organization. The importance of career development also involves a successful appointment of employees in positions that meet their desires as well as organizational requirements. Employee career development relates to organizational efficiency and can also result to more dedicated personnel and employee retention (Slum, 2004). Furthermore, Jennings (2005) stated that career stagnation occurs when one stays in one position for too long, affecting employee`s loyalty, commitment and willingness to stay.

One way of distinguishing by training is an alternative as it enhances broad attractiveness and observes high levels of commitment (Barrow & Mosley, 2005). Particularly specialized workplace

training initiated by the company improves the perception towards the company (Green et al., 2000). Career development seems to have an impact on expected quality of the employee experience. Past studies; (Taylor, 2002; Gaffney, 2005; Chabbra and Mishra, 2008), suggest that employees choose to stay longer where they experience individual growth and acquisition of specialized skills. Additionally, Porter & Steers' (1973) found out that work, development opportunities are expected to increase retention as individuals who sense that they are rewarded reasonably for the work done are more contented and fulfilled (Hausknecht, Rodda & Howard, 2009).

Remuneration is what employees receive in exchange for their work. This includes total remuneration in pay and benefits. Appropriate remuneration of the highly skilled business educators in Colleges of Education could be an effective tool for motivation and obtaining higher level of job attraction and retention as well as enhancing the college overall effectiveness. Additionally, the college ought to follow a remuneration program which aims at attracting and keeping the desired quality and mix of staff. Remuneration programs must be competitive enough both to attract and to retain the right talent/highly skilled business educators and incentive plans must focus on the most critical priorities of the college.

Friendly and good remuneration scheme is one of the very vital characteristics of retention because it fulfils the monetary and material needs (Walsh & Taylor, 2007). Salary retirement and job security have been shown to be important personal issues that may affect the satisfaction of faculty members in colleges and universities. The study found that less than half of the faculty members in national research indicated that they were satisfied with their salary and fringe benefits. According to Kreitner (2004), paying low salaries often means that top performers leave their jobs and others who might not be as good take these jobs. In addition to the salaries and wages, well rounded benefits such as health plans, insurance and pension plans offered to employees sends a powerful message to the employees that they are important. A company can retain their employees based on the fact that if the employees leave their job, they might not be able to replace the benefits they are getting by moving to a new company. Raises are also important especially if given at a time when other employers might not be giving them as they usually keep the employees motivated (Walker, 2004).

As a matter of importance, the reward management culture variables ought to be in their right proportion and distributed fairly to business educators in Colleges of Education for colleges to stand the chance of attracting and at the same time retaining the highly skilled and qualified business educators to their fold. This is in line with Adams (1963) equity theory of motivation, which calls for a fair balance to be struck between employee's inputs for example, efforts, tolerance, skill levels, hard work and enthusiasm, and employee's output, for example benefits, salary, compensation and recognition. According to this theory a fair balance serves to ensure a strong and productive relationship with the employees, with the overall result being satisfied. The reverse of this scenario in any organization often time results in employee turnover as in the case of colleges of education in Nigeria.

Employee turnover is a symptom of deeper issues that have not been resolved, which may include absence of a clear career path, lack of recognition, poor employee management relationships, salary, incentive payments, promotion, physical work environment to mention but a few. A lack of satisfaction emanating from poor implementation of reward practices may cause a business educator to withdraw and begin to look out for better opportunities. Highly skilled business educators remain assets to any College of Education, and their retention could be a factor to college success. The more experienced an employee is, the more valuable he is likely to be to the organization. Management of Colleges of Education and other relevant stakeholders, therefore, should take the issue of attraction of its highly skilled business educators as a top priority.

Statement of the Problem

There has been a constant mobility of the highly skilled persons/lecturers from Colleges of Education to other public sectors for better remuneration and conducive working environments among others (National Commission for Colleges of Education, 2012). This was amplified by Umaru and Danjuma (2017) who noted that the consequence of lack of job satisfaction resulting from poor reward practices in the College of Education set-up is reflected in the shortage of competent and committed lecturers. The highly skilled business educators in Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta States are not left out from this ugly trend.

The job turnover of the highly skilled business educators is believed to have affected the performance of business education students' graduates from College of Education in the corporate world of business. When organization's most experienced people leave for better greener pastures, a vacuum in intellectual knowledge is created. This has a devastating effect on business, influencing the value of the products and service delivery; it also increases the cost of replacement and recruitment of new staff. The poor reward management culture in Colleges of Education may likely lead to a display of dysfunctional behaviour to duties and unwillingness to lecture the students.

From the researchers' observation, there seems to be a widespread discontentment among the highly skilled business educators in most Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta States. There appears to be lack of staff career development and effective remuneration system. There also seems to be deliberate denial of basic incentive such as regular payment of salaries, allowances as well as poor condition of service among others in most Colleges of Education in Nigeria. The extent to which reward management culture in Colleges of Education correlate with job retention of business educators is however not clear to the researchers. The question therefore is, how do reward management culture correlate job retention of business educators in colleges of education in Nigeria?

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to ascertain the extent to which reward management culture correlate job retention of business educators in Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta State. Specifically, the study determined:

1. the relationship between career and business educators job retention in colleges of education; and
2. whether employee's remuneration correlates business educators job retention in colleges of education.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between career development and business educators job retention in colleges of education in Edo and Delta States?
2. What is the relationship between remuneration and business educators' job retention in colleges of education in Edo and Delta States?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. Career development and remuneration of Business Educators do not significantly predict job attraction in colleges of education in Edo and Delta states.

Method

The research design adopted for this study is a correlational survey. A correlational research design measures two or more relevant variables and assesses the relationship between or among variables, as well as allows the prediction of future events from the present available knowledge (Creswell, 2012). The population of the study comprised all the business educators in the six (6) public Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta States in Nigeria. The total number of business educators in these colleges is one hundred and thirty-three (133). The sample size was 133 respondents which represents 100% of the total population of the study. The entire population was used as the sample size because the population of the study is of manageable size, hence a census. The instrument that was used for data collection for the study is a structured questionnaire titled: "Reward Management Culture, Job Attraction Questionnaire of Business Educators in Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta States (RMCJAQ)". The questionnaire is divided into two sections; Section A, focused on respondent's biodata such as institution's location while Section B contains twenty-four (24) item statement made up of three (3) clusters that measured career development, employee remuneration and retention. Response to each item was rated on a 4-point modified Likert rating scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA); Agree (A); Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD), and were weighted as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. To ensure face and content validity, the instrument was validated by three specialists in Business Education. To establish the reliability of the instrument

for the study, Cronbach’s alpha Model was used. Cronbach alpha value of 0.80. These figures were considered appropriate for the purpose of this study. The instrument was administered to the respondents by the researchers with the help of five research assistants. The data collected were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Multiple Regression Analysis. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answer the research questions and Multiple Regression Analysis was to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Decision rule for the research questions was based on boundary limits where any calculated r-value between 0.0 and 0.19 was regarded as very low correlation, between 0.20 and 0.39 was regarded as low correlation, between 0.40 and 0.59 was regarded as moderate correlation, between 0.60 and 0.79 was regarded as high correlation and between 0.80 and 1.00 was regarded as very high (Ajayi & Abanobi, 2017). The decision rule for the hypothesis was based on p- value; when p-value was greater than .05 was retained, otherwise was Rejected

Result

Research Question One: What is the relationship between career development and Business Educators job retention in Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta State?

Table 1

Pearson r Showing the Relationship between Career Development and Business Educators Job Retention

Variables	N	r	Remark
Career Development	133	-.512	Moderate/Inverse Relationship

Job Retention

Key: Any calculated r-value between 0.40 and 0.59 was regarded as moderate

The results in Table 1 shows the relationship between career development culture and Business Educators job retention. The coefficient value obtained for career development and job retention is -.512 which means negative but moderate relationship. It therefore means that the relationship between career development culture and Business Educators job retention in Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta State is negatively or inversely Moderate

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between remuneration and Business Educators job retention in Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta State?

Table 2

Pearson r Showing the Relationship between Remuneration and Business Educators Job Retention

Variables	N	r	Remark
Remuneration Culture	133	.633	High/Positive Relationship
Job Retention			

Key: Any calculated r-value between 0.60 and 0.79 was regarded as high

The data presented in Table 2 represents the relationship between remuneration and Business educators job retention. The table shows that the correlation coefficient that exists between remuneration culture and Business Educators job retention is .633 which indicates positive but high correlation. This therefore means that the relationship between remuneration culture and Business Educators job retention in Colleges of Education in Edo and Delta State is positively high.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Career development and remuneration of Business Educators do not significantly predict job attraction in College of Education in Edo and Delta States.

Table 3

Summary of ANOVA on the Multiple Regression Estimates between Career Development, Remuneration and Recognition and Business Educators Job Retention

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	18.352	4	4.588	64.358	.000
Residual	9.125	128	.071		
Total	27.476	132			

The data analysis presented in Table 3 reveals that the ANOVA summary of multiple regression based on job retention as predicted by career development and remuneration culture of Business Educators is statistically significant ($F(4, 128) = 64.358, p = .000 < .05$). Thus, the null hypothesis which state that career development and remuneration of Business Educators do not significantly predict job retention in College of Education in Edo and Delta States is rejected. This means that career development and remuneration are significant predictors of job retention of Business Educators in College of Education in Edo and Delta States.

Table 4

Model Summary of career development and remuneration predicting Business Educators job retention

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	.817 ^a	.668	.658	.26700

Table 4 depicts that the r-value and r-square value obtained were .817 and .668 respectively. The adjusted R square value is .658, which indicates that the 65.8% of the variance in business educators’ job retention is explained by career development and remuneration. This value is a large effect (Cohen, 1988). From the overall model analysis, the null hypothesis is rejected. However, the model analysis shows that the reward management culture dimensions that have more predictive effect on Business Educators’ job retention is career development.

Table 5

Multiple Regression Coefficients on Career Development and Remuneration Predicting Business Educators Job Retention

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	1.749	.350		5.003	.000
Career Development	-.257	.076	-.223	-3.407	.001
Remuneration	.089	.113	.061	.791	.430

a. Dependent Variable: Job Retention

The data presented in Table 5 indicates that career development(p=.001) of the reward management culture dimensions predicting business educators job retention was found to be significant while remuneration (p = .430) was not significant. This indicates that career development is more interest to us. In other words, career development is more useful to job retention of business educators in colleges of education even though collectively reward management culture variables were found to be significant predictors of business educator’s retention.

Discussion Findings

The investigation carried out by the researchers on the first research question which ascertained the relationship between career development and Business educators job retention in colleges of education in Edo and Delta States shows that the co-efficient between career development initiatives and job retention is negative but moderate. It therefore indicates that the relationship between career development and Business educators job retention is negatively moderate. This implies that there is a lot of randomness affecting one or both variables in question, or perhaps other variables affect the two in question, therefore the direct relationship is not strong/high but it is certainly noticeable. Thus, there is a relationship but certainly not a high one, nor is it so low. Hence, moderate. The findings concur with Mappelu and Jumah (2013) who observed that employee career development has negative significant with employee job retention. The findings

also concur with the suggestions from (Taylor, 2002; Gaffney, 2005; Chhabra and Mishra, 2008), people normally reside longer where they experience individual and career growth and development. Also, based on Porter and Steers (1973) research, development opportunities are expected to increase retention rate as employees who feel they are fairly compensated for the work done are more contented. Similarly, Dockel (2006) observed that employees seem to grow a sense of responsibility (normative commitment) and stay longer in an organization that promotes career opportunity through learning and ability to apply acquired competencies. The findings also align with the findings of Hossieni (2010) who reported that among the eight dimensions of quality of work of life, pay fair and adequate pay size, integration and social cohesion, continuing security, the integration and development opportunities, are related to employee attraction and retention. Similarly, the findings concur with the recent survey on employee retention by Deloitte Kenya (2014) which found out that the biggest challenge facing most companies in Kenya is the inability to attraction and retain talent within their firms. Poor talent attraction and retention according to the survey is as a result of ineffective career development program (Deloitte Kenya, 2014).

The results of the analysis of the data relating to the second research question which determined the relationship between remuneration culture and Business educators job retention in colleges of education in Edo and Delta States shows that remuneration culture has a positive and high relationship with job retention. It therefore indicated that the relationship between remuneration culture and Business educators job retention is positively high. The implication of this is that, both remuneration culture and job retention of Business educators are moving towards the same direction. That implies that, an increase in remuneration packages will equally lead to an increase in job retention of Business educators. The findings agree with Norah (2017) findings that remuneration had a positive and significant relationship with employee retention. The findings of the present study also correspond with Heng and Quazi (2003) who affirmed that competitive pay packages are considered as one of the most popular and highly effective strategies that any organization can use. Similarly, the findings concur with studies conducted by Noordin and Jusoff (2009) and Mustapha (2013) who reported that salary/ remuneration has a significant effect on lecturers' level of attraction and retention. This also aligned with the study by Shoaib, Noor, Tirmiz, and Barshir (2009) who found that attractive remuneration packages are some of the important factors that affect talent attraction and retention.

On testing the hypothesis, the ANOVA summary table of multiple regression based on job retention of Business educators as predicted by career development and remuneration, was found that the p-value was less than the alpha value. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that career development and remuneration are significant predictors of job retention of Business educators in colleges of education. However, from the multiple regression coefficients table, some of the reward management culture dimensions predicting job retention of Business educators was significant such as career development while, remuneration was not significant. However, from the overall model analysis, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the results reveal that the reward management culture dimensions that have more predictive effect on Business educators

job retention is career development. The findings agree with the study by Chitalu (2011), whose finding showed that one of the key factors of attracting and retaining talented employee is through training and career development opportunities. This is consistent with the findings of Meathfield (2008), that career development opportunities have a significant influence on employee retention. On remuneration, the findings disagreed with Wambugu and Ombui (2013) findings that remuneration had a significant influence on Employee's job retention. The findings however agreed with Tizazu (2013) that remuneration has a positive relationship on employee's job retention. The implication of this, is that even though remuneration is found not to be statistically significant with Business educators job retention, it does help in reducing employees` job turnover because it revealed that there is a relationship.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that reward management culture variables are determinants of business educator's job attraction and retention in colleges of education in Edo and Delta States. In other words, reward management culture collectively predicts retention of business educators. It was further concluded that reward management culture variables of career development and remuneration were fundamental requirements that could promote job attraction and retention of business educators in colleges of education in South-South Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Colleges of education should strive to invest in the training/development of business educators which will not only help maintain their core competencies also enhance their job satisfaction and Attraction
2. Colleges of education academic staff union should strive to ensure remuneration packages to colleges of education lecturers especially to Business educator are attractive. They should go extra miles to making remuneration not just a tool to attract but also to retain business educators in colleges of education.
3. Colleges of education academic staff union should strive to ensure remuneration packages to colleges of education lecturers especially to Business educator are attractive. They should go extra mile to making remuneration not just a tool to attract but also to retain business educators in Colleges of Education

References

- Adams, J. S. (1963). 'Towards an Understanding of Inequity'. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67, 422-436
- Ajayi, P.O & Abanobi, C.C (2017). *Educational Research: A Fundamental Guide*. Rupee-Com Publishers & Coy. Asaba, Delta State-Nigeria
- Armstrong, M. (2010). *Armstrong's Essential Human Resource Management Practice: A Guide to People Management*. London: Kogan Page Ltd

- Barrow, S & Mosley, R. (2005). *The Employer Brand: Bringing the Best of Brand Management to People at Work*. London. Publisher- John Wiley & Sons Ltd, 2005-232 Pages.
- Creswell, J.W. (2012). *Educational Research Planning, Conducting and Evaluating Quantitative and qualitative Research*. (4th ed.) Boston, MA Pearson
- Chhabra, N.L. & Mishra, A., (2008). Talent Management and employer branding: Retention battle strategies. *The Icfai Journal of Management research*, 7(11), 50-61.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *National policy on education* (4th ed.) Lagos : Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council
- Gaffney, S., (2005). Career Development as a Retention and Succession Planning Tool. *Journal for Quality & Participation*. 28(3), 7-10.
- Hausknecht, J.P., Rodda, J. & Howard, M.J. (2009). Targeted employee retention: Heng, C.T., & Quazi, H.A (2003). Finders, Keepers Attracting, *Human Resources Management Journal* Motivating and Retaining Knowledge Workers. Vol.13(4)23-44
- Hossieni, S.M. (2010). Quality of Work Life (QWL) and its Relationship with performance of Social Insurance Workers of Mazandaran Province. Islamic Azad University, Firookoooh.
- Hytter, A. (2007). Retention strategies in France and Sweden. *The Irish Journal of Management*
- Jennifer, A. & Carsen, J.D. (2005). *HR How To- Employee Retention*. Chicago: CCH Knowledge point
- Kreitner, R. (2004). *Management*. 9th ed. Boston, USA: Houghton Miffling Company.
- Kwenin, D.O., Muathe, S. & Nzulwa, R. (2013). The influence of employee rewards, human resource policies and job satisfaction on the retention of employees Vodafone Ghana limited. *European Journal of Business and Management*. 5(12):12-13
- Mapelu, I.C. & Jumah, L., (2013). Effect of Training and Development on Employee Turnover in Selected Medium Sized Hotels in Kisumu City, Kenya. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Sports*, 1(3), 23.
- Musa, A., Amed C., & Bella, K. (2014). Reducing turnover in tertiary institutions in Ghana: The role of motivation. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(18), 115-135
- Mustapha, N. (2013). The influence of financial reward on job satisfaction among academic employees at public universities in Kelantan, Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. 4(3):244-248
- Noe, R.A., Hollenbeck J.R., Gerhart, B. & Wright P.M. (2006). *Human resource management: Gaining a competitive advantage*. 5th edition. New York: McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc
- Noordin, F., & Jusoff, K (2009). Levels of job satisfaction amongst Malaysian academic staff. *Asian Social Science Journal*, 5(5): 122-126
- Norah, S. (2017). Effects of reward management practices on employee retention in the hotel industry. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Department of Human Resource management. University of Agriculture and Technology, Jomo Kenya
- Porter, L.W. & Steers, R.M., (1973). Organizational work, and personal factors in employee turnover and absenteeism. *Psychological Bulletin*, (80), 151- 168.
- Shoaib, M., Noor A., Tirmizi, S., & Bashir, S. (2009). Determinants of employee Retention in Telecom Sector of Pakistan. Proceedings 2nd CBRC, Lahore, Pakistan. 14 November, 2009.
- Taylor, S., (2002). 'Recruitment, Selection and Induction'. In: *The Employee Retention Handbook*. London: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development, CIPD, pp. 155-180.
- Umaru, R.I & Danjuma, A.O (2017). Determinants of job satisfaction of colleges of education

Lecturers: A study of Nasarawa state college of education, Akwanga. *Asian Business Research Journal* vol.2(1)pp8-13

Walker J. W. (2001). *Perspectives human resource planning*, 2(1):6-10